

Study of synergic effect of trioctyl phosphine oxide on the solvent extraction of cobalt(II)-TTA complex

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Abstract : Liquid-liquid extraction of cobalt(II) with theonyl trifluoro acetone (TTA) and enhancement effects of trioctyl phosphine oxide on such extractions in various organic media have been studied by radiotracer technique. Strong ternary adduct complex formation were reported. Effect of temperature variation established such processes as spontaneous, enthalpy favoured with net loss in entropy. Synergic effects were reported to be strongly diluent dependent and regular solution theory was found to be applicable in such systems.

Keywords : Cobalt(II), β -diketone (TTA), regular solution theory.

Introduction

Liquid-liquid extraction of metal chelate having an excess of coordination site is markedly enhanced by the addition of neutral ligand forming adduct complexes in organic phase. A great deal of interest has been focussed on such synergistic extraction of *f*- and *d*-block elements specially in a combination of β -diketones and Lewis bases like organophosphorous esters¹. The degree of synergism depends not only on the properties of extractants but also on the kind of solvents. Since, synergistic effects are ascribed to the adduct formation in the organic layers, such changes must be explained in terms of the stability of adduct complexes in various media.

Considerable attention has been paid to several factors affecting adduct formation e.g. the structure of chelating agent², basicity of donor molecules³ or the size of central metal ion⁴.

Besides the solvent also plays an important role and the magnitude of formation constant of adduct changes with the kind of solvent⁵. Physicochemical properties of the solvent will influence both the distribution coefficients and the equilibrium constants of the organic phase reaction because the activity coefficient of a chemical species is known to be very sensitive to the medium. Activity coefficients may be estimated with the aid of regular solution theory⁶ and thus, the adduct formation constants

can be correlated to the changes in activity, in terms of the effect of solvent^{7,8}.

The effect of temperature is another important factor in studying the synergic reactions which allows the elucidation of the trend in thermodynamic parameters and establishes the extraction mechanism. Thus, synergic extraction of Co^{II} by HTTA and TBP⁹ was reported to be an entropy driven process while the evaluation of the thermodynamic constants of Co^{II}-HTTA-Db 18C6 in mixed organic solvent¹⁰ system explained extraction in terms of dehydration of extracted chelate to form the adduct. On the other hand, thermodynamic data of Co-HTTA-R₃PO system¹¹ indicates that the mechanism responsible for synergism in Co^{II} is one in which one water molecule from inner coordination sphere is displaced by synergistic base molecules. Again, studies of temperature effect on solvent extraction of Zr^{IV} from different aqueous media have established the dependence of extraction mechanism on both the diluents and also on the environment¹².

In present investigation, synergistic effects of trioctyl phosphine oxide (TOPO) on the extraction of Co^{II} with theonyl trifluoro acetone (TTA) is being reported. Although a wide number of research works have been reported on the solvent extraction of cobalt(II) from different aqueous media, studies on mixed extraction of cobalt is very limited^{13,14}. The present investigation reports extensive study of synergistic enhancement by the influ-

ence of TOPO on the extraction of Co^{II} by the β -diketone TTA, in terms of both temperature and diluent effect. Application of regular solution theory to such systems have also been shown to hold good.

Results and discussion

Optimisation of extraction condition :

The effects of organic solvents on the extraction of cobalt(II) with the ligand was studied separately and it was found that maximum extraction of metal corresponded to ethylacetate solvent. The trend of extraction with TTA was in the order : nitrobenzene < chloroform < carbontetrachloride << cyclohexane < diisopropylether < *n*-butanol < ethylacetate (Table 1).

Table 1. Distribution coefficient (D_o) of Co^{II} with chelating ligand (TTA) in different solvents [TTA] = 0.1 mol dm⁻³, pH = 2.1

Solvent	D_o	%E
Ethylacetate	1.5650 ± 0.100	61.01
Butanol	0.9078 ± 0.030	47.58
Diisopropylether	0.8298 ± 0.025	45.34
Cyclohexane	0.3829 ± 0.015	27.68
Carbontetrachloride	0.3516 ± 0.020	26.01
Chloroform	0.2189 ± 0.008	17.95
Nitrobenzene	0.2099 ± 0.070	17.34

The extractions of cobalt(II) using the complexing agent was studied under different pH condition of aqueous solution. It was observed that maximum extraction of Co^{II} by the ligand corresponded to an aqueous pH 2.1. As TTA is a weak monobasic acid, its dissociation is favoured in low acid medium and extraction by TTA, in turn, increases with increasing pH of the medium. However at higher pH, hydrolytic species of the metal disfavors the extraction of the metal and pH ~ 2 is an optimum condition for extraction of Co^{II} -TTA complex.

Extraction of cobalt(II) with individual extractant :

Extraction of Co^{II} from aqueous medium was investigated using various concentration of the ligand. The percentage of extractions were found to increase with increase in ligand concentration. At higher concentration of ligand, effective stripping of the water molecules take place from the hydrated cobalt ion sphere, rendering the species much more organophilic in nature. The log-log plot (Fig. 1) of the variation of distribution coefficient of

Fig. 1. Variation of distribution coefficient (D_o) of Co^{II} with TTA into different solvents. [TTA] is expressed in mol dm⁻³ and pH of aqueous solution = 2.1.

cobalt (D_o) against ligand concentration yielded straight line of slope ~2 for all the solvents used, establishing the presence of two bidentate chelating groups surrounding the cation [(eq. 1). If 'k' is the extraction equilibrium constant for the binary system, it is obviously related to distribution coefficient by eq. (2).

$$\log k = \log D_o - 2\log [\text{HA}] - 2\text{pH} \quad (2)$$

The organophosphorous compound, trioctyl phosphine oxide (TOPO) was found to have negligible extractability of Co^{II} under the present condition, so throughout the whole procedure the extraction with TOPO alone was neglected.

Synergistic extraction of cobalt(II) complex in presence of TOPO :

The distribution ratio of Co^{II} extracted with fixed amount of HA (TTA) increases by the addition of organophosphorous compound (TOPO) which itself under present condition has no extractability for Co^{II} . This is attributable to the formation of a more lipophilic adduct with this donor. In the ternary extraction system, plot of corresponding distribution coefficient D_{mix} against log [HA] yielded slope of ~2 (Fig. 2) while the log D_{mix} vs log [S] plot showed straight line behavior with a slope of ~1 (Fig. 3) suggesting extraction of the species of the type $\text{Co}(\text{A})_2(\text{S})$ in organic phase. The overall reaction of the generally accepted synergistic extraction of Co^{II} is given by eq. (3) where there are two molecules of HA

Fig. 2. The plot of $\log D_{\text{mix}}$ vs $\log [\text{TTA}]$ in synergistic extraction of Co^{II} in presence of fixed concentration of TOPO in different solvents. $[\text{TOPO}] = 0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 2.1$.

Fig. 3. The plot of $\log D_{\text{mix}}$ vs $\log [\text{TOPO}]$ in synergistic extraction of Co^{II} with TTA into different solvents. $[\text{TTA}] = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 2.1$.

and one molecule of donor (S) in the extracted adduct¹¹.

overall extraction constant (K) in ternary system is given by,

$$K = \frac{[\text{CoA}_2(\text{S})]_{\text{org}} [\text{H}^+]^2_{\text{aq}}}{[\text{Co}^{2+}]_{\text{aq}} [\text{HA}]^2_{\text{org}} [\text{S}]_{\text{org}}} \quad (4)$$

And it is related with distribution coefficient D_{mix} by eq. (5),

$$\log K = \log (D_{\text{mix}} - D_0) - 2\log[\text{HA}] - \log [\text{S}] - 2\text{pH} \quad (5)$$

The adduct formation reaction in the organic phase may be represented as,

And accordingly,

$$\log K_s = \log K - \log k \quad (7)$$

where k , K and K_s stand for binary, ternary equilibrium constants and formation constant of adduct in organic phase. All these equations are applicable to the ligand dissolved in different diluents. In Table 4 equilibrium constants for binary and ternary systems, calculated accordingly, are presented. Formation of comparatively strong adduct for TTA complex in several diluents medium is evident from the results.

It is interesting to note that for both binary extraction and ternary adduct formation processes, ethylacetate is the best solvent corresponding to maximum value of D_0 and K_s . Thus, adduct formation reactions are highly dependent on the nature of diluents. The experimental data for synergistic effects of TOPO on the extraction of cobalt with the given ligand are shown in Table 2. Obviously percentage of extraction and S.C. increase with donor concentration of the ligand. Synergistic coefficient

Table 2. Extractions of Co^{II} with TTA in presence of varying concentration of TOPO

$D_s = 0$, $[\text{TTA}] = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 2.1$,
concentration unit = mol dm^{-3}

Solvent	[TOPO]	D_0	D_{mix}	%E	S.C.	$\beta (\text{mol}^{-1})$
Ethylacetate	0.01		3.56	78.07	0.356	131.27
	0.015	1.5650	5.03	83.41	0.507	147.60
	0.02		6.11	85.94	0.592	145.21
Butanol	0.01		1.98	66.44	0.338	118.11
	0.015	0.9078	2.81	73.75	0.491	139.69
	0.02		3.41	77.32	0.575	137.82
Diisopropylether	0.01		2.01	66.77	0.384	142.23
	0.015	0.8298	2.68	72.83	0.509	148.64
	0.02		3.32	76.85	0.602	150.04
Cyclohexane	0.01		0.97	49.24	0.403	153.32
	0.015	0.3829	1.23	55.15	0.507	147.48
	0.02		1.78	64.02	0.667	182.43
Carbon-tetrachloride	0.01		0.88	46.81	0.398	150.28
	0.015	0.3516	1.15	53.48	0.515	151.38
	0.02		1.43	58.84	0.609	153.35
Chloroform	0.01		0.52	34.21	0.375	137.55
	0.015	0.2189	0.71	41.52	0.511	149.56
	0.02		0.99	49.74	0.655	176.13

(S.C.) and apparent formation constant of ternary complex (β) are defined as,

$$\text{S.C.} = \log D_{\text{mix}}/(D_o + D_s), D_s = 0 \text{ (here)}$$

$$\text{and } \beta = (D_{\text{mix}} - D_o)/D_o[\text{donor}]$$

where, D_o and D_s are distribution coefficients of metal in presence of pure ligand and donor only. In all the cases the role of solvents were remarkable. Tremendous synergic effect is observed in case of some of the solvents and such effect is different for different solvent system reflected by S.C. values. Hence extent of synergism depends upon the nature of solvent.

Thermodynamic parameters :

Extractions of Co^{II} by the mixture of β -diketone and TOPO were also studied as a function of temperature ($20\text{--}60^\circ$) and the thermodynamic parameters like enthalpy of formation (ΔH_f°), entropy of formation (ΔS_f°) and free energy changes (ΔG_f°) were calculated by the use of Gibbs-Helmholtz eq. (8),

$$\log K = \frac{-\Delta H_f^\circ}{2.303 RT} + \frac{\Delta S_f^\circ}{2.303 R} \quad (8)$$

The enthalpy of formation (ΔH_f°) and entropy of formation (ΔS_f°) of the extraction processes were calculated from the slope and intercept of the plot of $\log K$ against $1/T$ (Fig. 4). The lines in these plots were obtained through the linear regression analysis. The values of (ΔH_f°) and (ΔS_f°) along with (ΔG_f°) values were calculated from the

Fig. 4. Effect of temperature on the extraction constant of Co^{II} with TTA in presence of TOPO into different solvents.

plots, and given in Table 4. The data clearly show that extraction process proceeds spontaneously in the forward direction ($\Delta G^\circ < 0$). However, trends in ΔH° and ΔS° values for the chelating extractions can be explained only by the structures of metal chelates.

When metal cations form innersphere complex with the donor molecules, entropy term is favoured and enthalpy term is disfavoured i.e. reaction is endothermic in nature due to the total disruption of hydration sphere and liberation of large number of water molecules causes gain in entropy. On the other hand, for outer sphere complexes, both enthalpy and entropy changes are negative. Owing to the complexation, there is decrease in randomness without a compensatory disruption of the hydration sphere (Table 4) shows that cobalt(II) forms outer sphere complexes with TTA. Negative value of ΔS suggests that the reaction accompanies a reduction in the number of molecules and species of higher freedom are ordered together to give one extractable complex. Thus, Co^{II} -TTA chelate in either tetrahedral or square planer geometry forms ternary adducts by expanding its coordination shell and changing the geometry to square pyramidal structure, as suggested by Marcus and Kertes¹. A negative value of ΔH is expected because there is no accompanying dissociation reaction. Overall mechanism appears to differ from that suggested by Kandil and Ramadan¹¹ for the formation of similar ternary adduct complexes. However such experiment was performed in benzene solvent and this implies that the solvent has a very important role in deciding the course of complex formation reaction.

Effect of diluents :

As previously mentioned, synergistic extraction proceeds via ternary adduct formation in organic phase. Thus the nature of the organic solvent is expected to have an effect in deciding the path and also the extent of synergism. In Table 2 enhancement effect of TOPO on Co^{II} β -diketonate extraction in different organic solvents are presented and results show that wide variation of S.C. takes place for different diluents. Dielectric constants for later have practically no correlation with such results. Equilibrium constants for ternary systems (Table 3) also vary accordingly. However such results may be explained by the regular solution theory⁶ which may be used to calculate the activity and activity coefficients of interacting species.

Table 3. Equilibrium constants for binary and ternary systems of Co^{II}

System	Binary systems		Ternary systems		
	Solvent	log <i>k</i>	Donor	log <i>k</i>	log <i>k_s</i>
Co-TTA	Ethylacetate	-1.62	TOPO	1.28	2.89
	Butanol	-1.85		1.03	2.87
	Diisopropylether	-0.89		1.01	2.89
	Cyclohexane	-2.23		0.67	2.86
	Carbontetrachloride	-2.26		0.64	2.88
	Chloroform	-2.46		0.43	2.83

Table 4. Thermodynamic parameters related to ternary systems of the metal complex

System	Solvent	ΔH°	ΔS°	ΔG°
		(kJ K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	(JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	(kJ K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)
Co-TTA- TOPO	Ethylacetate	-10.71	-10.9	-7.73
	Butanol	-10.75	-15.6	-6.49
	Diisopropylether	-7.25	-5.02	-5.89
	Cyclohexane	-7.22	-11.22	-4.12
	Carbontetrachloride	-8.71	-16.31	-4.33
	Chloroform	-9.03	-21.01	-3.31

The thermodynamic equilibrium constant K_s^0 for adduct formation reaction in organic phase,

is given by

$$K_s^0 = a_{\text{adduct}}/a_{\text{chelate}} \cdot a_{\text{donor}} = k_s \cdot F_y$$

where, $F_y = Y_{MA_2(S)}/Y_{MA_2} \cdot Y_S$

$$\text{and } K_s = C_{MA_2(S)}/C_{MA_2} \cdot C_S$$

where, *a* and *y* represent activity and activity coefficient respectively. In these set of equations, MA₂(S), MA₂ and S represent ternary chelate donor adduct of metal, metal chelate and pure donor respectively. When the activity coefficient of pure component is taken as constant, the value of K_s^0 may be considered to be independent on the solvent. Under this condition, plot of log K_s against log F_y is expected to give straight line with slope ~ -1 . Activity coefficients may be determined from Hildebrand's regular solution theory,

$$\log F_y = -2B\delta_{\text{org}} + \log V_{\text{org}} \cdot V_{MA_2(S)} / V_{MA_2} \cdot V_S + C - 1/2.3 \quad (9)$$

where, *V* and δ are molar volumes and solubility parameter and two terms *B* and *C* are given by⁵⁻⁷,

$$B = 1/2.3 RT (V_{MA_2(S)} \cdot \delta_{MA_2(S)} - V_{MA_2} \cdot \delta_{MA_2} - V_S \delta_S) \quad (10)$$

$$C = 1/2.3 RT (V_{MA_2(S)} \cdot \delta_{MA_2(S)}^2 - V_{MA_2} \cdot \delta_{MA_2}^2 - V_S \delta_S^2) \quad (11)$$

In eq. (9), only δ_{org} and V_{org} are related to diluent properties. Solubility parameter of chelate is assumed to be same as that of ligand e.g.

$$\delta_{\text{Co-TTA}} = \delta_{\text{TTA}} = 9.9$$

Molar volumes of chelate is taken to be $3V_{\text{ligand}}$ as three molecules of ligands are involved in the complex.

For ternary adducts, molar volume is the sum of those of chelate and donor, while solubility parameter is calculated from

$$\delta_{MA_2S} = 2.3 RT/2V_{MA_2S} (\delta_1 - \delta_2) [\log k_{s_1}/k_{s_2} + \log v_1/v_2] + (V_{MA_2} \cdot \delta_{MA_2} + V_S \delta_S)/V_{MA_2S} \quad (12)$$

where the subscripts 1 and 2 corresponds to the parameters of the solvent pair in which $\delta_1 - \delta_2 \geq 0.5$. Substituting the values of solubility parameters for all solvents¹⁶, ligand⁵ and donors⁵ in eq. (9), it was possible to calculate value of log F_y for individual solvent system. The values of log K_s for β diketonates in different organic solvents used here have already been determined experimentally and shown in Table 3. A linear plot (Fig. 5) with slope ~ -1.00 establishes the applicability of regular solution theory in case of Co^{II}- β -diketone-TOPO systems. The formation constants K_s^0 in the activities was estimated to be $\sim 2.91 \pm 0.05$ for TTA-adduct. Thus the regularity in the ternary adduct formation in different media can be

Fig. 5. Variation of log K_s of ternary adduct of Co^{II} against log F_y [$F_y = Y_{\text{adduct}}/Y_{\text{chelate}} \cdot Y_{\text{donor}}$, *Y* = activity coefficients].

explained by change in activity coefficients. It is also possible to obtain useful information on an estimation of equilibrium constant or a choice of suitable solvent for a particular metal chelate extraction system. The enhancement effect of a particular donor in various diluent is comparable from such studies. Validity of regular solution theory in calculation of activity coefficient in all these cases has been assumed to be acceptable as the solvents have no specific interaction with the solutes.

Experimental

The chelating ligand theonyl-trifluoro acetone (TTA) and donor tri-octylphosphine oxide (TOPO) were obtained from Aldrich, USA. All the solvents used in present work e.g. butanol, chloroform, ethylacetate, cyclohexane, nitrobenzene, carbontetrachloride, diisopropylether were purified by standard procedures. All other reagents used were of A.R. grade. A stock solution of Co^{II} was obtained by dissolving $\text{CoSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in deionised water and standardised by gravimetry. A given aliquot of stock solution so prepared was treated with NH_4OH and the precipitate of $\text{Co}(\text{OH})_2$ was dissolved in minimum volume of 1 : 4 HCl. It was added with little amount of tracer ^{60}Co , supplied as CoCl_2 by BRIT, India and finally made up to the mark. A Systronics model 335 digital pH-meter equipped with a single electrode was used for pH measurement. A single channel γ -ray spectrometer coupled with a well-type NaI (T1) detector of Nucleonix, India make was used for radioactivity measurement. The radioisotope ^{60}Co was assayed by its characteristic photopeak.

Extraction procedure :

In the general extraction procedure, 5 ml aqueous solution containing $\sim 50 \mu\text{g}$ spiked Co^{II} was adjusted to an aqueous pH 2.1 and extracted with equal volume of different solvents containing the chelating ligand, for a period of 30 min in a mechanical shaker. For synergistic study, organic phase of the ligand was mixed with tri-octyl phosphine oxide (TOPO) reagent of desired concentration. After the equilibration, two phases were separated and radio-activities of equal volumes (1 ml) of each of the two phases were measured. Distribution coeffi-

cients (D) were computed from,

$$D = \frac{\text{Radioactivity in organic phase}}{\text{Radioactivity in aqueous phase}}$$

Material-balance in the extraction was checked from the counts of two phases separately.

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